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THE USE OF GENERATIVE NEURAL NETWORKS IN PROCEDURAL MODELING OF GAME WORLDS

Abstract. The article explores the application of generative neural networks in procedural modeling of game worlds, enabling the automation of game content creation, including levels, scenarios, 3D objects, textures, and NPC behavior. The study aims to analyze the role of generative neural networks in shaping game environments, identify key types of generated content, and examine modern algorithms and models that enhance procedural generation. The study employed general scientific methods of cognition based on analysis, synthesis, comparison of scientific literature, and expert publications. The findings indicate that generative neural networks serve as a crucial tool in procedural content creation. They facilitate the efficient automation of game design development, significantly reducing the time required to construct game environments. The study identified key types of generated content, including graphical elements, audio components, spatial structures, interaction systems, storylines, balancing mechanics, and other supplementary data. The analysis revealed that different neural network architectures are applied to generate various aspects of the gaming experience. Specifically, convolutional neural networks are used for processing images and textures; recurrent neural networks generate scripts and event sequences; autoencoders compress and optimize data; while generative adversarial networks (GANs) create realistic objects and structures. Advanced technologies enhance 3D visualization and automated game object generation, contributing to the development of more realistic and logically structured gaming environments. The study suggests that future developments in neural networks will focus on integrating different generation methods and improving training datasets to enhance content quality. The practical significance of the research lies in its potential to reduce video game development costs while increasing the level of detail and realism in virtual worlds, opening new prospects for the gaming industry.

Keywords: generative neural networks, procedural modeling, game design, PCG, 3D visualization.

Problem statement. The development of game environments is undergoing a revolutionary transformation driven by artificial intelligence technologies. Modern developers are increasingly integrating AI, particularly generative neural networks, at every stage of video game creation. One of the most common applications of these technologies is character development and their adaptation to various game environments.

An analysis of contemporary gaming products and the technologies behind them reveals a continuous improvement in graphics quality and the level of detail in game worlds. These environments are becoming more flexible, personalized, and interactive. This progress is largely driven by growing consumer expectations, as players seek more automated, dynamic, and unconventional gaming experiences. End users, in turn, anticipate deeper personalization, unique storylines, and greater variability in gameplay. In this context, artificial intelligence demonstrates some of the most advanced capabilities. Research on neural networks helps identify new, effective approaches to the evolution of the gaming industry, opening up opportunities for further optimization of game development processes and enhancing player immersion in virtual worlds.

Analysis of recent scientific research and publications. The use of generative neural networks in procedural modeling of game worlds has been extensively covered in scientific literature. A. Amato made a significant contribution to this field by analyzing key approaches to procedural content generation in the gaming industry [1]. N. Barriga provides an overview of procedural generation algorithms used in video games, highlighting their advantages and limitations [3].

The study by M.Hendriks, S.Meijer, Van Der Velden, and A. Iosup offers a comprehensive review of procedural content generation (PCG) methods in video games, covering both classical and modern algorithms [5]. V. Kumaran, B. Mott, and J. Lester explore the possibility of generating game levels for various games within a shared latent space, presenting new opportunities for applying generative models in game development [6].

N. Anantrasirichai and D. Bull examine the role of artificial intelligence in creative industries, including video games, emphasizing the significance of generative models in developing new approaches to content creation [2]. X. Mao, W. Yu, K. Yamada, and M. Zielewski [7] investigate the use of generative AI in procedural content generation, while S. Mohaghegh, M. Dehnavi, G. Abdollahinejad, and Hashemi [8] propose the PCGPT model based on transformers, demonstrating the potential for further advancements in this technology.

Beyond academic sources, contemporary aspects of neural network applications in game development are discussed in expert publications, including an

article on the Habr platform [4], which analyzes the latest trends and practical cases of implementing generative AI in the gaming industry.

Despite the abundance of research on this topic, there is a lack of systematic material that consolidates existing approaches and methodologies. Therefore, this study organizes and presents the analyzed information according to the research theme, utilizing various scientific cognition methods.

The aim of the article is to demonstrate how generative neural networks are used for modeling game worlds.

Presentation of the main material. Procedural content generation (PCG) refers to a set of methods that utilize artificial intelligence algorithms to create game levels, worlds, and various elements. In a game environment, these elements are diverse and are constructed from bits, which serve as a fundamental building material for spatial modeling, system and scenario design, derivative content, and more.

Table 1

Types of content in a game environment

Type of content	Description
Bits	These are the smallest elements that form the game world. They include textures, sound effects, object models, animations, behavioral scripts for characters and objects, and particle systems (e.g., fire, smoke, water, magical effects). For example, generating trees in forests or random texture patterns for surfaces.
Space	Responsible for the procedural generation of world geometry. This includes interior spaces (corridors, rooms, dungeons, caves), outdoor locations (forests, deserts, fields, cities), bodies of water (lakes, rivers, seas), and special zones (teleportation portals, mountains, cliffs). Examples include level generation in roguelike games or the automatic creation of open worlds in games like No Man's Sky.
Systems	These mechanisms ensure dynamics and interaction within the game world. They include ecosystems (balance of flora and fauna), transportation networks (roads, railways), urban infrastructure (buildings, markets, institutions), and NPC behavior systems (AI, player interaction, behavioral changes based on in-game events). Examples include procedurally generated road networks in cities or NPC reactions to player actions in RPGs.
Scenarios	Responsible for constructing narrative elements of the game. This includes randomly generated puzzles, missions, cutscenes, quests, and the overall game progression structure (unlocking new levels, events, story arcs). In The Binding of Isaac, each run generates a new set of challenges, while in Minecraft, random tasks can be created for players.
Design	Procedural generation of the game's internal logic. This covers both game mechanics (rules, balance, difficulty levels) and the overall world design (theme, style, atmosphere). Procedural methods can create different combat balance variations, resource distribution, and mechanics tailored to different player types. In Slay the Spire, each run offers different card combinations that influence gameplay style.
Derived content	Secondary content formed based on player interactions or gameplay data analysis algorithms. This includes automatically updated in-game news, live stream records, leaderboards, and gameplay statistics. In Dark Souls, players can see the ghosts of other players, while in Counter-Strike, ranking tables and match statistics are generated.

Note: systematized by the author based on [3;5]

The primary reason for implementing procedural content generation is cost reduction in content creation. It decreases the need for large memory volumes and minimizes manual labor for developers. Modern games often feature vast worlds that require hundreds of hours to design manually. PCG enables small teams to develop large-scale, high-quality games that can compete with projects from major studios by leveraging generative neural networks.

PCG has been used in video games since the 1980s. The first game to adopt this approach was *Rogue* (1980), where each playthrough generated unique dungeons, enemy placements, and item distributions. While the generation was largely based on randomness, the game employed algorithmic rules to maintain balance. For example, room placement followed specific patterns to prevent the creation of unplayable levels.

Thus, procedural generation not only simplifies development but also introduces new opportunities for game design, expanding the boundaries of gameplay experiences [7].

Neural networks play a crucial role in game content creation. They can automatically generate textures, 3D models, scripts, NPC behavior, and even music. Various types of neural networks are used, including convolutional, recurrent, autoencoders, and generative models. Their key features are outlined in Table 2.

Table 2

Types of neural networks used in game programming

Type of neural network	Description
Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)	Deep neural networks designed for processing two-dimensional structures, such as images. They contain convolutional layers that apply filters to input data, extracting key features. CNNs are widely used for image enhancement, object recognition, noise reduction, resolution upscaling, and automatic colorization of black-and-white images.
Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)	Used for analyzing and generating sequential data. Their connections allow them to consider previous context when processing new elements in a sequence. This makes them effective for tasks such as speech recognition, handwriting analysis, music composition, and text generation. RNNs are commonly applied in chatbots, voice assistants, and language models.
Autoencoders	Neural networks designed to reconstruct input data through compression and subsequent expansion. They are used for extracting essential features, noise reduction, data compression, and generating new samples similar to the original ones. Autoencoders are applied in dimensionality reduction, image restoration, and the creation of generalized data representations.
Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)	Consist of two components: a generator, which creates new data samples, and a discriminator, which evaluates whether the data is real or artificially generated. GANs are widely used for generating realistic images, videos, and audio, creating characters in video games, stylizing artwork, and producing photorealistic faces of non-existent people.

Note: systematized by the author based on [2; 9; 10]

Each type of neural network incorporates specific technologies that have been successfully implemented in game development software. For example, NeRF (Neural Radiance Fields) enables neural networks to synthesize 3D objects from 2D images, opening new possibilities for realistic visualization. In the field of generative systems, the Sloyd platform creates 3D models based on text input. While it can currently generate simple objects and architectural elements, it is not yet capable of producing complex characters or animations [4].

The most widely used technologies for generating game environments are outlined in Table 3.

Table 3

Technologies used for generating game environments

Technology	Description
NeRF (Neural Radiance Fields)	Used for rendering volumetric scenes through machine learning, enabling the creation of 3D objects from 2D images.
GAN for textures (StyleGAN, Pix2Pix)	Allows the generation of realistic textures for objects and characters.
Super-Resolution AI algorithms	Enhance texture quality by upscaling images without losing detail.
GPT-3 / GPT-4 for NPC dialogues	Used to generate dynamic conversations and adaptive responses.
RNN for quest generation	Enables the creation of quests that change based on player actions.
SEED (EA) for NPC self-learning	Used to develop NPCs that adapt to a player's gameplay style.

Generative neural networks can be used for the automatic construction of game environments, including terrain generation, object placement within scenes, surface texturing, 3D model creation, and real-time adaptation of the game world. These technologies enable developers to quickly generate complex scenes with minimal human intervention.

The most common objects created using generative neural networks are outlined in Table 4.

Table 4

Objects generated by neural networks for game environment creation

Generated objects	Description
Terrain generation	Uses generative neural networks to create realistic surfaces, mountains, water bodies, and vegetation.
Automatic object placement	Neural networks position 3D objects based on the given context, accelerating the level design process.
Texture generation	Deep learning algorithms produce detailed textures that adapt to the surrounding environment.
Dynamic environment adaptation	The game world changes in response to player actions or the game scenario, enhancing realism.

Landscapes can be generated using various technologies. The first is Perlin noise, which creates smooth natural gradients, allowing for the generation of realistic terrain that blends seamlessly into game environments. The second technology is Voronoi noise, which divides space into distinct cells around random points and assigns them textures resembling natural materials. Developers can choose from different types of natural materials, such as stone, sand, and soil. Another technology involves generative neural networks, particularly generative adversarial networks (GANs). This approach reconstructs three-dimensional shapes based on pre-existing two-dimensional images, adding highly detailed and realistic elements. Overall, combining these methods enables the creation of unique and complex natural landscapes that would be challenging to implement manually.

With these technologies, developers can significantly accelerate the creation of game scenarios. For example, generative models can generate a detailed ecosystem that includes various natural elements such as plants, trees, rocks, and other objects within the game environment. To ensure that the generated content meets the developer's requirements, clear procedures and rules must be established. These instructions are created by specialists with expertise in programming, game composition, and variation design.

By defining specific templates or guidelines and integrating them into an AI-driven development environment, a ready-to-use product can be generated, tested, and further refined if necessary. This approach automates the game environment creation process. Some developers claim that by using generative networks, development time can be reduced by up to 50%.

Today, developers have introduced a wide range of software tools that enable either the automatic generation or enhancement of textures. These include neural networks such as StyleGAN and Pix2Pix. These technologies utilize complex, highly detailed textures that seamlessly map onto objects of various geometric shapes. While language models and neural networks significantly improve the quality of game assets, it is worth noting that the creative approach to character design by AI has not yet surpassed the capabilities of traditional manual programming.

However, at a sufficiently advanced level, artificial intelligence is already capable of generating dynamic dialogues based on the environment in which the player finds themselves. Additionally, recurrent neural networks are actively used to create nonlinear narratives and quests, adjusting event sequences according to the player's previous choices. These decision trees play a key role in procedural modeling, ensuring that in-game events vary based on the scenario and conditions encountered by the player.

In story-driven games, player choices can profoundly influence the plot, leading to different dynamic outcomes. Decision trees allow for the creation of complex narrative structures and nonlinear gameplay experiences, enhancing immersion in the game world.

The behavior of non-player characters (NPCs) is modeled using reinforcement learning algorithms. One example is EA's SEED system, which employs self-learning agents to create NPCs that adapt to each player's individual playstyle. These agents are particularly effective in multiplayer environments, where they dynamically adjust their behavior based on player strategies and current game conditions.

Considering recent advancements in generative AI for procedural game content creation, future technologies are expected to focus on improving content quality and simplifying its implementation. Enhancing quality is a natural stage of development, and achieving this requires the application of various approaches. Another key factor in future technological progress is improving the usability of generative models. Since complex technologies are not always quickly adopted by the industry, adapting them to developers' needs and simplifying implementation processes will promote their widespread use in game development. One promising approach to improving game content quality is the integration of multiple technologies, allowing for the creation of more realistic and flexible game worlds.

An intriguing research direction involves exploring GANs' latent space through search algorithms, which help identify content that meets strict criteria. Another promising approach is integrating different types of neural networks capable of processing multimodal input data, significantly expanding content generation possibilities. A crucial factor affecting the quality of generated content is the diversity and volume of training datasets. Studies indicate that some datasets are not efficiently processed by language models, necessitating either manual adjustments or extensive modifications to the generated content. One potential solution to this issue is data augmentation—a technique that modifies training data during the model's training process to prevent overfitting. However, this approach is not always effective in game world development, as it may distort the structure and logic of procedural generation.

Overall, artificial intelligence and language models are expected to continue advancing in specialized areas optimized for specific tasks. It is likely that dedicated neural networks will be developed for game environment creation, designed to better understand the nuances of various tasks while considering the needs of both clients and developers, ultimately enhancing the quality of game content.

Conclusions. Generative neural networks have become an essential component of procedural game world modeling, enabling the automation of level generation, scenario adaptation, 3D object creation, texture synthesis, and NPC behavior. The main types of generated content include bits (core graphical and audio elements), space (world geometry), systems (NPC interactions, infrastructure), scenarios (quests, missions), design (balance, mechanics), and derived content (statistics, rankings). Various neural networks are actively used in content generation: CNNs for image processing, RNNs for handling sequences, autoencoders for data

compression, and GANs for generating realistic objects. Advanced technologies like NeRF and Sloyd expand the possibilities for 3D visualization and automated object creation, making PCG a key tool in modern game design. Generative neural networks significantly accelerate game environment creation by automatically generating landscapes, textures, 3D models, and real-time adaptive environments. The use of noise algorithms (Perlin, Voronoi) and neural networks (GAN, NeRF) ensures realistic and logically structured game spaces. Object placement and texture generation algorithms (StyleGAN, Pix2Pix) improve scene detail. Language models (GPT-3, GPT-4) and RNNs provide dynamic storytelling and NPC behavior, while self-learning agents (SEED) adapt NPCs to a player's gaming style. Future PCG research will focus on integrating multiple generation methods, improving training data, and simplifying the use of AI technologies for game developers.

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